

Artificial Gravity

Can controlled non-ferromagnetic magnetism create it?

Abstract

A magnet is a material or object that produces a magnetic field. This magnetic field is invisible but is responsible for the most notable property of a magnet: a force that pulls on other ferromagnetic materials, such as iron, and attracts or repels other magnets.

Body

In this photo, the floor is made up of magnets that produce a controlled force to create an artificial pull/gravity around the object (which in this case is a person). The problem is: can we use its force for non-ferromagnetic objects so we can create artificial gravity?

Notes

The implications of this scientific achievement will be great because it will enable astronauts and future people to travel into space more efficiently, reliably, and eliminate negative aspects of non-gravity in space.

Conclusion

Using magnets to create a controlled force on non-ferromagnetic objects can make it possible for future space crafts, space stations, and other planetary habitats to simulate gravity, thus making those habitats more adapt to support human life.

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